

From: [Sletteemeås, Jannice Schau](#)
To: sophie.granier@anses.fr; Jean-Yves.MADEC@anses.fr; Marisa.haenni@anses.fr;
Muna.Anjum@apha.gsi.gov.uk; mirjam.grobbe@bfr.bund.de; alexandra.irrgang@bfr.bund.de;
sven.maurischat@bfr.bund.de; jetk@food.dtu.dk; alessia.franco@izslt.it; antonio.battisti@izslt.it;
e.m.broens@uu.nl; Sletteemeås, Jannice Schau; Sunde, Marianne; Matthew.Ellington@phe.gov.uk;
Neil.Woodford@phe.gov.uk; wasy@piwet.pulawy.pl; cindy.dierikx@rivm.nl; thijs.bosch@rivm.nl;
AMA@ssi.dk; stefan.borjesson@sva.se; marit.pringle@sva.se; kees.veldman@wur.nl
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Dear consortium members,

First of all, I hope this newsletter finds you well. It has been a strange year due to the COVID crisis. Nevertheless, I think we should consider ourselves privileged that we were able to continue working on research projects.

The OH-EJP IMPART consortium thankfully received a budget-neutral extension of one year. This gave us the opportunity to finish the tasks agreed upon thanks to the efforts of all partners involved! Next year, we want to publish our results and hope for your support to accomplish this.

Finally, the IMPART management team will organize an **on-line closing meeting in March 2021**. We hope you will be able to join us (please reply to this link; https://doodle.com/poll/4xdzaeswqvfsxdz3?utm_source=poll&utm_medium=link by **January 20**). For now, we wish you all a Merry Christmas and a Happy New Year!

Please read a short update from the different WP leaders below.

The WP1 final ring trial report was sent to the participants and uploaded on the EJP website in November 2020. As a result, PCR detection of *mcr*-genes showed 100% specificity and CHROMID[®] Colistin R demonstrated a better sensitivity compared to CHROMagar[™] COL-APSE and COLISTIGRAM to isolate colistin-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae*. Performance of the colistin-resistant screening process is greater for caecal than meat samples in the experimental conditions of this WP1. More trials are needed to test the effect of other matrixes, bacterial concentrations and a broader range of *mcr*-positive strains before defining a proposal for monitoring resistance to colistin. A draft article of this work package is planned to be sent to the participants in the first months of 2021.

In WP2, the main work in 2020 was to analyze the results from the final ring trial held in September 2019. The report from was finished and published on the OH-EJP website in September 2020. The main outcome indicates that some of the commercially available selective agar media are not sensitive or selective enough to detect bacteria expressing low-level carbapenemase production. Further, there are no commercially available selective agars to detect carbapenem-resistant *Salmonella* spp.. In addition, some bacteria harboring specific genes that circulate in the livestock population in Europe might be missed using the protocol currently set by the EU decision 2013/652/EU with a pre-enrichment in non-selective BPW-ISO. In October, a small group comprising Cindy Dierikx, Stefan Börjesson, Märít Pringle and Jannice Schau Sletteemeås started drafting a manuscript on the results from this work package. This draft will be circulated among the participants in this work package.

Within WP3, 1,310 MIC-distributions were collected from nine partner institutes consisting of 47,640 MIC-values involving 19 different veterinary pathogenic bacteria. All MIC distributions

have been uploaded on to the EUCAST database. However, the progress in setting new ECOFFs has been delayed because recently EUCAST became stricter on the acceptance of MIC-distributions with regard to the methods used for MIC-testing. As a consequence, WBVR is currently performing bridging studies testing a selection of streptococci and *Pasteurella multocida* isolates to determine the possible effect of using CAMHB + LHB (according to CLSI) instead of MH-F broth (according to EUCAST). Finally, the first ECOFFs for *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* and *S. hyicus* are expected in the beginning of 2021.

In WP4, 527 *Clostridioides difficile* strains from several collaborate institutes have been characterized by PCR-ribotyping, toxin gene detection and phenotypic resistance testing (determination of minimum inhibitory concentrations - MICs). In parallel, inhibition zone diameters (IZD) were determined using an optimized disk diffusion protocol that was also the basis for a ring trial to finally validate this method. This ring trial was conducted in summer 2020 and reports were sent to all participants. A final report of this ring trial will be uploaded to the EJP website in January 2021. This ring-trial revealed a good interlaboratory reproducibility but also critical factors that influence test results. Finally, the agar dilution based MICs and IZDs of the 527 *C. difficile* strains correlated very well for most but not all antimicrobials tested which implies that disk diffusion can substitute agar dilution for most but not all antimicrobials. A manuscript will be drafted within the first quarter of 2021.

Best wishes,
IMPART WP leaders